

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Perception towards Pharmacovigilance among Undergraduate Medical Students and Pharmacy Students

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Abstract:

Background: The discovery and quantification of adverse drug reactions has long relied on the careful analysis of spontaneously reported cases. Causality assessment was a fundamental feature of individual case report analysis. This was complemented by analysis of aggregated cases, and of disproportionality analyses in spontaneous reports databases. The main of the study is assess of knowledge, attitude, and perception towards pharmacovigilance among undergraduate medical students and pharmacy students.

Materials and Methods: A Prospective Cross-sectional, pre-validated questionnaire based survey was performed among 150 undergraduate students in Rangaraya medical college, and PYDAH College of pharmacy, Kakinada to understand the Knowledge, Attitude, and Perception of undergraduate and Pharmacy Students about pharmacovigilance. Students interviewed using questions sent through Google Forms and printed forms, descriptive statistics were used for the analysis of data and the results were expressed as percentage (%).

Results: The majority of students (92%) demonstrated adequate knowledge of pharmacovigilance principles and its significance. A high proportion (90%) were familiar with ADR, reflecting a strong understanding of its clinical importance. 80% of students had seen ADR reporting forms, indicating moderate exposure to ADR documentation. 86% were aware of the ADR reporting procedure, showing good preparedness for pharmacovigilance activities. 90% knew about regional pharmacovigilance centers, highlighting their theoretical understanding of the pharmacovigilance framework. Nearly all students (98%) agreed that ADR reporting improves patient safety, suggesting a positive attitude toward pharmacovigilance. However, only 8% reported submitting an ADR, revealing a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

Conclusion: Our study highlights a lack of awareness among students about pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting, emphasizing the need for enhanced medical curricula to bridge this knowledge gap.

Keywords: Pharmacovigilance, Adverse drug reaction, Students, Pharmacy, Medical.

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Introduction

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are a major cause of illness and place a significant burden on healthcare systems, both in terms of patient health and economic costs. Research shows that ADRs contribute to 2.4% to 6.5% of hospital admissions, with many of these being preventable. In India, the rate of serious ADRs is reported to be 6.7% [1].

The World Health Organization defines pharmacovigilance as the "science and activities related to the detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related issues" [2]. Many drug-related harms, such as drug interactions, food-drug interactions, and specific toxicities, often go unnoticed until years

after a drug has been introduced. Some rare side effects, which occur in roughly 1 in 100,000 cases, are only identified once the drug is widely used [3,4]. The identification of these rare adverse effects depends heavily on comprehensive pharmacovigilance efforts. Pharmacovigilance programs (PP) have played a key role in detecting ADRs and have led to the withdrawal of several drugs from the market. However, these programs face the significant challenge of ADR under-reporting.

Given differences in healthcare systems and drug access, experts suggest that each country develop its own pharmacovigilance program [5,6]. Various

methods are used to detect adverse events (AEs), such as spontaneous reporting and prescription event monitoring. Doctors reporting AEs to ADR databases through these methods can be critical in identifying rare and unexpected reactions. However, there is a noticeable gap in physicians' knowledge and practices regarding ADR reporting [7-9]. Several factors contribute to under-reporting, including time constraints, the perception that reporting a single case is not important, concerns about added workload, and the fear of legal repercussions [10,11].

This study aims to assess and evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) regarding pharmacovigilance among medical students at a tertiary care hospital.

Material and Methods

A prospective, cross-sectional study was conducted using a pre-validated questionnaire to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of pharmacovigilance among undergraduate students.

The survey involved a total of 150 participants, comprising medical students from Rangaraya Medical College, Kakinada, and pharmacy students from PYDAH College of Pharmacy, Kakinada. The study was carried out over a five-month period, from September 2022 to January 2023.

Data were collected using a structured 24-item questionnaire distributed via Google Forms and printed formats to ensure broad accessibility.

The questionnaire was designed to assess the participants' understanding of pharmacovigilance, attitudes towards its importance, and their perceptions of adverse drug reaction (ADR) reporting practices. Descriptive statistical methods

were employed to analyze the collected data, with the results presented as percentages (%) to provide a clear representation of the findings.

Results

The majority of students (92%) demonstrated adequate knowledge about pharmacovigilance principles and its significance (Figure 1).

A high proportion of students (90%) were familiar with ADR, indicating a robust understanding of its clinical importance (Figure 2). 80% of students had seen ADR reporting forms, reflecting moderate exposure to the practical aspects of ADR documentation (Figure 3). 86% of the students knew the procedure for reporting ADRs, signifying a favorable level of preparedness for contributing to pharmacovigilance activities (Figure 4). 90% percent of the students were aware of the existence and function of regional pharmacovigilance centers, underscoring their theoretical knowledge of the pharmacovigilance framework (Figure 5). Almost all students (98%) agreed that ADR reporting contributes to enhancing patient safety, indicating a positive attitude toward pharmacovigilance practices (Figure 6). Despite the high levels of knowledge and awareness, only 8% of students reported having submitted an ADR to a pharmacovigilance center, highlighting a significant gap between theoretical knowledge and practical implementation (Figure 7).

These results demonstrate a strong foundation of knowledge among students regarding pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting, but they also emphasize the need for improved practical engagement and training to bridge the gap between awareness and practice.

Figure 1: Knowledge about Pharmacovigilance

Figure 2: Knowledge about ADR

Figure 3: Students who have seen ADR forms

Figure 4: Students who know how to report ADR

Figure 5: Knowledge about regional pharmacovigilance center

Figure 6: Students who agreed that reporting ADR will increase patient safety

Figure 7: Students who reported ADR to pharmacovigilance center

Discussion

In this study, 92% of the respondents demonstrated knowledge of pharmacovigilance, while 90% were aware of ADR reporting. Additionally, 80% of students reported having seen ADR reporting forms. This contrasts with the findings of Gupta and Udupa, who observed that only 43% of participants were familiar with ADR reporting.

In our study, however, over 90% of students were knowledgeable about both pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting [11]. Despite this strong theoretical understanding and a positive attitude toward pharmacovigilance, only 8% of respondents had reported an ADR.

This discrepancy suggests a gap between knowledge and actual practice, possibly due to the emphasis placed on teaching the importance of pharmacovigilance rather than encouraging its practical application.

The growing recognition of pharmacovigilance's importance has led to the development of both international and national pharmacovigilance programs (PP), with 90% of respondents aware of regional pharmacovigilance centers. However, fewer were familiar with nationwide programs, a finding that contrasts with the study by Gupta and Udupa, where only 43% of participants were aware of India's National Pharmacovigilance Centers [11]. Similarly, Oshikoya and Awobusuyi's study in Nigeria showed that only 51.5% of doctors were aware of the national pharmacovigilance center [8].

Kutmi et al. reported that over 40% of MBBS students believed that ADR reporting was compulsory. In our study, more than 80% of students viewed ADR reporting as necessary, which aligns with Gupta and Udupa's findings where 89.5% of participants recognized the importance of ADR reporting [11,12]. Ponmary et al. also found that second-year MBBS students had a better understanding of pharmacovigilance compared to residents, while nurses demonstrated awareness of pharmacovigilance but lacked sufficient knowledge on how to report ADRs [6].

The findings from this study and others highlight a significant gap in ADR reporting practices, despite a generally favorable attitude toward it. Since doctors are usually the first point of contact for patients, it is essential to motivate and encourage them to report ADRs consistently [13,14].

This study employed a qualitative research methodology, which could be further enriched by including other healthcare professionals to gain a broader understanding of the current state of pharmacovigilance and to propose more effective measures.

Conclusion

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The results of our study reflect gaps in students' knowledge regarding pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting. Therefore, there is a need for an implementation of effective medical curricula to improve medical and pharmacy students' knowledge regarding pharmacovigilance and the adverse drug reporting.

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